

Researcher-Centred Data Collection
Survey and Focus Groups results

CoARA pilot project
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1. Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document provides a detailed account of the researcher-centred data collection activities carried out within the project *Towards a Qualitative Paradigm: Rethinking Research and Researchers Assessment at Blanquerna, Universitat Ramon Llull (ReAss)*, focusing on the survey and focus groups conducted with the researcher community. Its purpose is to document, in a transparent and systematic manner, the methodological procedures, instruments, and results that informed the design and implementation of the research assessment reform pilot.

Specifically, the document outlines the rationale and objectives of the data collection strategy, describes the instruments, details the data collection and analysis procedures, and presents the main findings derived from both approaches. By doing so, it provides the underlying evidence base for identifying strengths, weaknesses, overlooked dimensions, opportunities, and risks associated with the existing research assessment system.

The scope of this document is primarily methodological and empirical. It is intended to enhance the transparency, credibility, and reproducibility of the ReAss project by making explicit how researchers' perspectives were systematically gathered and analysed, and how these insights contributed to the definition of the project's dimensions of change and the development of assessment tools. While the findings are grounded in a specific institutional context, the approaches and lessons documented in this report may be of relevance to other organisations engaged in research assessment reform within the CoARA framework.

2. Overview of the Data Collection Strategy

The ReAss project implemented a researcher-centred data collection strategy combining an online survey and focus groups to gather evidence on researchers' perceptions of existing research assessment practices. The strategy aimed to capture insights into strengths, weaknesses, overlooked dimensions, opportunities for improvement, and perceived risks.

Both instruments were aligned with the CoARA principles, with particular attention to inclusivity across research career stages (R1–R4). The combined use of these two types of instruments, both qualitative but admitting different levels of depth in the information collected, provided complementary and consistent evidence to inform the co-creation of reform priorities and the design of assessment tools.

3. Survey Study

3.1. Survey Design and Development

The survey objective was to gather systematic evidence on researchers' perceptions of the existing research evaluation system at FPCEE–Blanquerna across all career stages, with

particular attention to perceived strengths, weaknesses, overlooked dimensions of research activity, opportunities for improvement, and potential risks.

The survey design and items development were informed by the longitudinal review of assessment practices and aligned with the principles of research assessment reform promoted by CoARA. Particular care was taken to ensure sensitivity to different research career stages, following the European Career Framework (R1–R4), in order to capture variations in experience and expectations across academic trajectories.

3.2. Survey Instrument

The questionnaire combined closed-ended and open-ended questions, allowing for both descriptive analysis and qualitative interpretation of the collected information. It was structured around five main thematic blocks:

1. Perceived strengths of Blanquerna's existing research evaluation system
2. Perceived weaknesses and problematic aspects of Blanquerna's existing research evaluation system
3. Research dimensions that are not sufficiently recognised by Blanquerna's existing research evaluation system.
4. Opportunities and proposals for improving the research evaluation system at Blanquerna.
5. Perceived risks and unintended effects of Blanquerna's existing research evaluation system

3.3. Participants and Sampling

The survey was sent to the research staff of FPCEE–Blanquerna. A total of 26 researchers responded, representing approximately 13% of the overall research population. This was a low response rate, likely due to two main reasons. First, data collection began in late May, at the end of the academic year, when the teaching evaluation period also began. We assumed this might be a better time to respond, since the teaching period was over. However, some potential participants contacted us, explaining that this was a particularly hectic period when they were too busy assessing reports, papers, and exams to add any other commitment to their agenda, such as completing the survey. A second reason might be the survey's topic, which was neither pleasant nor popular among many researchers. In recent years at the FPCEE, the way research has been assessed, particularly the quantitative approach used to evaluate researchers' productivity, was contested by some researchers. Since their comments were not addressed on previous occasions, it might be plausible that they did not feel it was worth responding to the survey. The final participants came from a range of academic programmes, including Psychology, Education, and Physical Activity and Sports Sciences.

To analyse differences across professional trajectories, responses were segmented by research career stage:

- R1 (First Stage Researcher): 15.4%
- R2 (Recognised Researcher): 7.7%
- R3 (Established Researcher): 38.5%
- R4 (Leading Researcher): 38.5%

While the sample size was modest, it provided insights into how the evaluation system is experienced across career stages.

3.4. Data Collection Procedure

The survey was administered online in June 2025. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed of the study's purpose and that their responses would be treated anonymously. The survey was disseminated through institutional communication channels, and responses were collected and stored in accordance with the institutional data protection and ethical standards.

3.5. Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics, including cluster and correlation analyses across dimensions, while open-ended responses were examined through qualitative content analysis. Responses were coded into thematic categories corresponding to the main survey blocks (dimensions) and further analysed to identify convergences and divergences across career stages. Once the category system was established, two researchers independently coded half of the information. Inter-rater agreement ranged from 80% to 96% across categories, indicating high reliability and allowing them to continue coding the remaining information.

4. Survey Results

The survey results reveal a balanced but critical view of the existing research evaluation system. While respondents acknowledged several strengths related to clarity and institutional commitment, they also identified significant limitations linked to metric dependency, insufficient recognition of diverse research contributions, and structural constraints affecting research activity.

Overall, perceptions of the research evaluation system showed a high degree of convergence across career stages, particularly regarding the perceived over-reliance on quantitative indicators, the limited recognition of diverse research contributions, and the need for more qualitative and contextualised assessment practices.

4.1. Perceived Strengths

Respondents most frequently valued the standardisation and transparency of evaluation criteria, followed by institutional acknowledgement and follow-up of research activity. They also valued the system's formative purpose as a strength, which was clearly declared but not always operationalised into practical measures.

Notably, the analysis identified career-stage-specific emphases that are worth noting. When referring to strengths, both early-stage and recognised researchers (R1–R2) tended to place greater emphasis on issues related to fairness, transparency, and career development. In contrast, established and leading researchers (R3–R4) more frequently emphasised structural and organisational constraints, such as workload distribution, role overload, and the sustainability of research activity over time.

Table 1

Main Perceived Strengths of the Research Evaluation System

Strength	Definition
Standardised criteria	Clarity and transparency in evaluation processes
Institutional follow-up	Recognition and monitoring of research activity
Formative purpose	Support for self-assessment and goal setting
Limited diversification	Initial inclusion of qualitative elements

4.2. Perceived Weaknesses and Unclear Aspects

The most recurrent weaknesses concerned the limited diversification of criteria, excessive reliance on bibliometric indicators, lack of support and resources for career development, and bureaucratic burden. Respondents also highlighted role overlap between research, teaching, and management as a structural constraint affecting research performance. No consistent differences across career stages were identified within this dimension.

4.3. Overlooked Dimensions of Research Activity

A central finding was the systematic under-recognition of knowledge transfer and social and economic impact, followed by interdisciplinary work and collaborative roles within research teams. Importantly, respondents explicitly identified the tension between individual and group-based assessment, anticipating the need to better align individual evaluation with collective research development.

Table 2
Most Frequently Identified Overlooked Dimensions

Overlooked Dimensions	Definition
Knowledge transfer; Social and economic impact	Research and Innovation activities with high societal relevance, value, and benefits that are insufficiently recognised in current assessment practices.
Interdisciplinary work	Research that integrates multiple disciplines but is poorly captured by current assessment criteria.
Individual–group tension	The lack of strategic alignment between individual and group development, whereby contributions related to building and sustaining research groups are undervalued under individual-focused evaluation models.

4.4. Opportunities for Improvement

Respondents proposed innovations centred on responsible and inclusive criteria, more efficient and integrated evaluation systems, stronger institutional support, and qualitative, flexible assessment models adapted to disciplinary diversity and career trajectories. Co-creation of evaluation criteria and leadership recognition also emerged as relevant, though less frequently cited.

4.5. Perceived Risks and Threats

The most salient perceived risk was the persistence of a quantity–quality imbalance, driven by external metric pressures. Other concerns included potential declines in research activity, ethical risks, misalignment with accreditation systems, talent drain, and a widening gap between research and society. These risks reinforced the need for reform grounded in qualitative judgement, transparency, and institutional support.

Taken together, the survey results provided a robust empirical foundation for the ReAss project. They directly informed the identification of the project’s dimensions of change and the design of the Narrative CV, assessment rubric, and capacity-building actions, ensuring that reform efforts were anchored in researchers’ experiences and expectations.

5. Focus Groups

As mentioned, as part of the researcher-centred data collection strategy, a series of online and face-to-face focus groups was conducted, particularly to reach researchers reluctant to complete the survey and to gather in-depth qualitative insights into researchers’ perceptions,

expectations, and concerns regarding the implementation of narrative-based research assessment.

5.1. Design and Objectives

All the focus groups were conceived as deliberative spaces to complement survey findings and to support collective reflection on the proposed reform. A total of 45 researchers from 5 research groups participated in the focus groups. Almost all participants (40) subsequently submitted a Narrative CV, thereby grounding the discussions in concrete experience with the new assessment tool. The sessions lasted approximately one hour and were moderated by members of the project team. Participation was voluntary, and contributions were anonymised for analysis.

The primary objectives of the focus groups were:

- To explore initial reactions to the Narrative CV and narrative assessment approach,
- To identify perceived opportunities and risks associated with its implementation,
- To surface cultural, organisational, and ethical considerations,
- To inform the definition and validation of the project's dimensions of change.

5.2. Data Collection and Analysis

The focus groups discussion followed a semi-structured guide organised around the project's dimensions of change and the core principles of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (CoARA). Thematic blocks addressed, among other aspects, were the conceptualisation of research quality, the role of narrative and qualitative assessment, inclusivity across career stages, recognition of diverse contributions and impacts, transparency and formative feedback, and the alignment between individual and group-based assessment. Sessions were recorded and supplemented with detailed notes.

A thematic qualitative analysis was conducted, following an inductive approach. Transcripts and notes were coded iteratively, allowing recurrent patterns and shared concerns to emerge from the data. This process resulted in the identification of seven key themes, which are presented below. Illustrative quotations are included to reflect participants' voices and to exemplify the main findings.

6. Focus Group Results

- Perceived Value and Opportunity of Narrative Evaluation
Participants consistently framed the narrative CV as an overall positive and transformative change.

“This new perspective on research has been very positively valued, but at the same time it also scared us because of the potential evaluation workload.”

“The first word that came to my mind was ‘opportunity.’ I see this as a more inclusive system, especially for those of us working in local innovation.”

“We should congratulate ourselves for this initiative—it reflects long-standing demands from the academic community.”

- **Cultural Change in Research Evaluation**

At the same time, the narrative approach was understood as a more profound shift in academic culture and values, acknowledging the complexity that accompanies its adoption.

“This represents a cultural change. We will need to put the project outputs up for discussion and collectively reflect on them.”

“The system couldn’t continue like this, dominated by large publishing corporations that we were forced to play along with.”

- **Recognition of Diverse Outputs and Research Impact**

In all the comments, participants highlighted the need to recognise forms of impact beyond traditional bibliometric indicators, which, in turn, were pointed out as the main weaknesses of the current research assessment approach.

“Narrative evaluation is not about inventing things; it’s about finding other metrics to demonstrate impact beyond journal quartiles.”

“We also want to recognise local impact—such as when a municipal government uses research to create a new wellbeing network for older adults.”

“Many fields rely heavily on books and this was not properly reflected.”

- **Inclusivity and Visibility of Previously Marginalised Work**

Some participants mentioned that the narrative CV can be an opportunity to make visible outputs and research-related work that they considered remained invisible in previous research assessment approaches.

“We face many barriers to publishing in high-impact journals, yet we are deeply involved in innovation projects with schools.”

“That part of our work used to remain invisible, and now it finally gains recognition and motivation.”

“The previous evaluation system pushed us away from certain types of innovation and applied research practices because they simply ‘didn’t count.’”

- **Concerns About Evaluation Implementation and Capacity**

Despite the positive comments, participants mentioned strong concerns around feasibility, expertise, and workload, both for the researchers to explain their research activity

and the evaluators to assess a greater diversity of research outputs and outcomes appropriately.

“Evaluating narrative CVs requires specific expertise, and right now I don’t see how we will be able to do it properly without extensive training.”

“With the previous method, it was easier to reach a conclusion.”

“Writing a narrative CV is challenging, and there is also a risk that those with stronger storytelling skills may be advantaged.”

“I liked the music but I’m not sure about the lyrics.”

- **Data Governance, Transparency, and Trust**

In the same vein, almost all the participants expressed the need for clarity regarding data use and dissemination, particularly because the pilot results were part of the Re-Ass project.

“One of our main concerns is how the data we provide in the narrative CV will be used.”

“Since this is a pilot, we would like clarity on what will be published—ideally, only outcomes, not personal data.”

- **Need for Feedback, Training, and Multilevel Evaluation**

For some participants, adopting a new research assessment approach, including the narrative CV, was considered a good way to move from summative to formative and supportive assessment feedback. The idea of combining different feedback levels was also mentioned for a few participants, as well as the use of the assessment results as inputs for career literacy development.

“We need formative feedback from the evaluation process.”

“We need to be strategic about what we include to explain our trajectory in a narrative CV.”

“We should combine different levels of feedback—individual, research group, and research institute.”

7. Integrated Analysis and Synthesis

The combined evidence from the survey and focus groups directly informed the identification and refinement of the project’s seven dimensions of change. Survey responses provided initial signals regarding gaps and priorities—such as the need to broaden the conceptualisation of research quality, to recognise societal impact, and to move beyond metric-driven evaluation—while focus group discussions played a decisive role in interpreting, validating, and collectively negotiating these priorities.

In particular, the focus groups enabled the transformation of perceived problems into shared reform directions, ensuring that the dimensions of change reflected not only analytical diagnosis but also researcher endorsement. Each dimension of change can be traced back to specific concerns, expectations, and proposals articulated by researchers across both data collection methods.

8. ReAss Dimensions of Change

1. **Broadening the Conceptualisation of Research Quality**

Moving beyond narrow, output-based definitions of excellence to recognise diverse forms of knowledge production, impact, and engagement, including open science, interdisciplinary work, and societal contribution.

2. **Embedding Qualitative, Narrative and Peer-Based Assessment**

Shifting the centre of assessment towards qualitative judgement supported by narrative accounts and peer review, with quantitative indicators used responsibly and contextually.

3. **Ensuring Researcher Development and Inclusivity Across Career Stages**

Designing assessment practices that are sensitive to different career phases (R1–R4), trajectories, and roles, and that support development rather than penalise non-linear careers.

4. **Enhancing Reflexivity, Transparency and Formative Feedback**

Strengthening dialogic assessment processes, clarity of criteria, and the formative function of evaluation in order to build trust, legitimacy, and learning-oriented assessment cultures.

5. **Fostering Researcher Engagement and Co-Creation**

Actively involving researchers in the design, discussion, and refinement of assessment criteria and tools, recognising engagement as a prerequisite for sustainable reform.

6. **Reframing the Role of Assessment in Career Progression**

Opening a structured, long-term discussion on how assessment outcomes relate to recognition, research time allocation, promotion, and career advancement, in alignment with CoARA principles.

7. **Aligning Individual and Group-Based Assessment to Support Sustainable Research Environments**

Addressing the tension between individual performance evaluation and collective research practices by recognising collaborative roles, team science, and shared

responsibility for research quality, with the aim of fostering resilient and sustainable research ecosystems.

9. Annexes

9.1. Survey Instrument

 [Annexe_Survey_Qüestionari del Sistema d'Avaluació de la Recerca Universitària FPC...](#)